

SILK HYDROGEL COMPOSITE SCAFFOLD CONTAINING HYDROXYAPATITE NANOCRYSTAL

Hyung Hwan Kim¹, Min Ji Kang¹, A Reum Park¹, Shin Hwan Kim¹, Young Hwan Park^{1*}

¹ Department of Biosystem and Biomaterial Engineering, Seoul National University, Seoul, Korea

* Corresponding author (nfchempf@snu.ac.kr)

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1 Introduction

We define hydrogel as a polymer network containing a large amount of water or biological fluid in a 3-D structure. Because of the physical or chemical chains present in a hydrogel, it is stable in aqueous environment. Therefore, it has been used in diverse medical fields. [1, 2] In addition, by controlling the gelation degree of polymer solution (the state prior to hydrogel) hydrogels can be easily applied to damaged tissue area. This unique structure and properties of hydrogel shares a similarity with ECM (Extracellular matrix) in that it has a potential to be applied in tissue engineering field. Especially, the injectable property and ECM like structure can be applied to bone regeneration. [3] Out of several polymers can be form hydrogels, silk fibroin (SF) has an excellent biocompatibility, biodegradability and it can be used to create bone regeneration scaffold in the form of hydrogel.

In this study, we fabricated a SF/Hydroxyapatite (HAp) composite scaffold. To improve the dispersibility of HAp in the SF aqueous solution, we chemically modified the surface of Hap particles using hyaluronic acid (HA) – dopamine (DA) conjugate. Since SF aqueous solution has a long term gelation time, we utilized ultra-sonication method to induce a rapid gelation. Morphological structure, mechanical properties, and biological properties were measured in order to evaluate the suitability of SF/HAp composite hydrogel as an injectable bone regenerative scaffold.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Preparation of the SF aqueous solution

For degumming, cocoons of *Bombyx mori* were boiled in a solution of sodium oleate and sodium carbonate cocktail solution at 105 °C. Degummed SF was dissolved in 9.3M lithium bromide solution at

60 °C for 30 minutes. Dissolved SF solution was dialyzed in cellulose dialysis tube for 3days.

2.2 HAp surface modification

First, HA and DA was conjugated in deionized water by EDC as a coupling reagent. Then, the purified HA-DA conjugate was stirred vigorously with HAp nanoparticles for the adhesion of catechol group of DA and HAp. Finally, HA-DA-HAp conjugate was rinsed in deionized water to remove the unreacted HA-DA conjugate.

2.3 Fabrication of SF/HAp hydrogel

SF aqueous solution was diluted to adjust the concentration of SF aqueous solution to 5% (w/v). Next, various concentrations (11, 25, 50 % (w/w) at fixed SF concentration) of surface modified HAp were mixed with SF aqueous solution. (Table. 1) Ultra-sonication was applied to induce the fast gelation of SF/HAp mixed solution and stored at 37 °C.

Sample	SF(%)	HAp(%)	SF : HAp
S5H0	5	0	-
S5H11	5	0.55	9:1
S5H25	5	1.25	4:1
S5H50	5	2.5	2:1

Table 1. Fabrication conditions of SF/HAp hydrogel.

2.4 Characterization

Dispersibility of HAp in SF hydrogel was evaluated by TGA. In addition, FE-SEM, FT-IR, WAXD and UTM were utilized for the comparison of physical and mechanical properties of various SF/HAp composite hydrogel.

MTT assay was carried out to evaluate the cell viability of various SF/HAp hydrogels using MC3T3-E1 cell line (osteoblast).

3 Results & Discussion

3.1 Morphological analysis of SF/HAp hydrogel

Three spots (top, middle, and bottom) of SF/modified HAp hydrogel and SF/unmodified HAp hydrogel were compared by TGA. SF/modified HAp hydrogel showed the same residual weight at all three spots. However, residual weights of three spots were different at SF/unmodified SF hydrogel. It can be explained by the low dispersibility of HAp in the aqueous solution. FE-SEM images(Figure 1) also showed that HAp were evenly dispersed in SF hydrogel structure and as the concentration of HAp increased, the density of HAp in SF hydrogel increased and had unique structure at S5H50 (highest HAp condition).

Fig 1. FE-SEM images of S5H0, S5H25, and S5H50 at X20000, X50000 magnification.

3.2 Structural and Mechanical analysis of SF/HAp hydrogel

FT-IR had clear peaks of SF and HAp. This indicates that SF (organic) and HAp (inorganic) were mixed well. In the WAXD data, SF hydrogel had a very broad peak at [200] ($2\theta=19.6$) and very small peak at [100] ($2\theta=8.7$) and [201] ($2\theta=23.3$). This is because SF hydrogel has a very low crystallinity compared to the natural SF or regenerated SF fiber. As the concentration of HAp increased, crystallinity of SF hydrogel decreased (the most broad peak ' $2\theta=19.6$ ' at S5H50).

In compression test, in spite of the low crystallinity of S5H50, S5H50 had the highest compression stress than the other hydrogels.

3.3 Biological analysis of SF/HAp hydrogel

MC3T3-E1 had good cell viability at day 1 in S5H0. As the HAp concentration increased, cell viability of MC3T3-E1 decreased at day 1. However, at day 7, cell viability of MC3T3-E1 in S5H50 was near the OD(optical density) of S5H0. Although, HAp had the negative effect on MC3T3-E1 cells on day 1, it consistently supported the proliferation of MC3T3-E1 cells for extended period of cell culturing.

4 Conclusions

The TGA and FE-SEM revealed that SF/HAp composite hydrogel was successfully fabricated and HAp was well dispersed within the SF hydrogel structure. As the HAp increases in the SF hydrogel, the crystallinity of SF hydrogel decreased and the compression strength was slightly increased. The MTT assay confirmed that HAp promoted the proliferation of MC3T3-E1 for culturing up to 7 days. Consequently, we believe that SF hydrogel containing HAp has a good cytocompatibility with a potential to be used as a bone regenerative scaffold.

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